

The State of the \$BBBYQ_ The colloquial butterfly

Sun, Feb 18, 2024 9:29AM 1:11:40

SUMMARY KEYWORDS

hudson bay, company, shares, reorganization, lazard, corporation, sixth street, divisive, stock, tax, ticker, furlong, gamestop, happening, ownership, ryan, sal, bed bath, day, butterfly

SPEAKERS

Jake2b, chadmojo, Sal

J Jake2b 01:36

Hey guys sorry Forgive me for taking a minute there I gotta get my life sorted out here trying to find some receptions just give me a moment guys and I gotta learn how to edit a title while we have a space going as well so just give me one second All right well I'm really excited that where we're hanging out tonight i appreciate everybody dedicating their time on a Gosh on a Saturday evening of I think a maybe even a long weekend depending on where you are. So I hope everyone's doing well. I'm just going to get some speakers and CO hosts up here and we'll get started guys just give me one sec

S Sal 02:21

repost please guys, spread the awareness of the space in the shadow band. I get DMS afterwards saying people couldn't join my space or didn't show up on their timeline or on the main page. So always just repost it help spread awareness. I'm 99% sure a lot of BBB y que stuff is Shadow band. And as a result, obviously they want us to shut up. We won't shut up. We will continue holding spaces. We will continue to be consistent. Spread the the spread awareness and repost the good messages.

J Jake2b 02:53

You can tell Sal's in a in a working mood without even saying hello, that's great, buddy. Appreciate it.

S Sal 02:59

Oh, sorry, my bad. Hello, Jake. Hello, Chad. Hello, everyone listening. Hey.

C chadmojo 03:04

Hey, guys, Jake. Just so you know, I held 10 minutes space hype space for this space. And let me tell you, you have so many people in here that are just super jacked.

J Jake2b 03:15

Oh, by the way, this this could be a new a new routine. This is fantastic.

C chadmojo 03:20

Yeah. Yeah. It's gonna be a thing. 2024

J Jake2b 03:24

Hey, 2024 is the year of hype spaces. I appreciate it. I think you titled it pregame actually, right? Oh, yeah. Oh, this is fantastic. Energy.

C chadmojo 03:33

Just feel it, use it and and just like spreads. But Edie?

J Jake2b 03:41

That's amazing, buddy. Thank you. Oh, my goodness. I love it.

S Sal 03:44

You know, Canadians are too well mannered. Just the mention of me saying hello. And stuff like that. It's not something we do in London. We kind of just walk into a friend's house and just sit down and just start talking to them. Reminds me of this joke from this comedian. He's from East London. His name is Mickey Flanagan. He's really, really funny. And he said, he went out to the pub with his friends came home. And his wife said to him, Okay, you're at the pub. He said, Yeah, I was with Terry and the boys. And she said, Oh, did you ask Terry how his wife is? And he said, Come to think of it. I didn't ask Terry how he was. And that is British. Kind of the way we are our etiquette. We just get on with it. No, hello, no. Hi. Just a quick stabbing.

J Jake2b 04:28

Well, you know what's funny is I'll share a funny story. The first time I spoke with Sal over the phone. The other thing you don't do is you don't say bye when you're done speaking. And so I thought, yeah, you're mad. I thought this was a really great call. And then all of a sudden, I was

like, Oh, now I have to question things. Now

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Sal 04:47

that's just, it's just Yes, just London Sr, where we are. We don't say hello and say bye. We just pick up the phone and say what do you want? And they'll be like, Oh, I'm in hospital dying and then you just hang up? Yeah,

J

Jake2b 04:57

it's no no. Why waste time right.

S

Sal 05:01

Yeah, I you know, because of you actually have become more well mannered. Now we speak regularly to discuss DD and stuff. And it's weird because I find myself saying stuff like, Okay, have a nice day. And then afterwards, my stomach feels weird. I have these like, rash forming on my hand. I'm like, What the hell is going on to me? Well,

J

Jake2b 05:20

you know, it's okay to have a little Canadian robot. Fine. Yeah, that's alright, man. Anyway, you know what, let's just get rolling. I appreciate everybody being here tonight. I don't want to have a super super long space tonight. Because I know it's the middle of the weekend. It's the most privy, not that the Privy Gosh, whoa, wow, the most most prime time real estate of everyone's week. So we don't want to take too much time. But I do want to share some great things that that have been discovered. Looking after the, you know, a lot of great work has been done into the whole butterfly thing. And, you know, there's been a lot of links that have been found a lot of really cool elements that have been discovered a lot of tendencies where Lazard specifically does a lot of this a lot of great work and digging by a lot of members of the community. And so tonight is just a little, I think it's gonna bring a couple of these ideas together, I think it's going to put another layer of understanding on top of all this, and it's going to be really good. And so we're talking about the butterfly tonight, and specifically the colloquial the colloquial butterfly, which just means, you know, using it in ordinary conversation, which is really what the butterfly is, you know, like, I'll give it a little quick synopsis here. We were all a bit surprised when we saw the renaming of the company revealed in the SEC filings, then we started looking into it and a lot of great work was done by folks to discover that you know, this is really not uncommon. And that oh my god, you had to do this gunk thing a that's, that's okay. You know what, you know what, you know how some some folks are making their profile picture the blackout thing. I'm gonna do the same thing, but I'm just gonna have a white stripe going across it in the middle.

S

Sal 07:00

That's why polti Did it. He's trying to show that

J Jake2b 07:05

from start to finish, My God, my hair cannot grow back quickly enough. But the thing is, is you know, we noticed Lazard actually using the butterfly. You know, Sal, you did a lot of really good work famous did a lot of good work. Dirty Vader did a lot of good work. CNN did a lot of good work in discovering these butterflies all over the place. CNN even found that Lazard was using it a different language is mentioning it in Italian and Spanish. And so you know, it's kind of funny, you know, I mean, on its face, it just felt like wow, maybe it's just Lazard's favorite animal or, you know, maybe they just enjoy insects a lot. But in fact, you know, the reason that Lazard is specifically uses Boyle

S Sal 07:42

is that they enjoy incest. Hello, I really miss.

J Jake2b 07:46

You see, you see, I mean, no, I don't want to make that joke that that's going a little bit too far. But, you know, so Lazard specifically, it's no coincidence that they're the ones doing this a lot. Because if you actually go to lizards website, which I mean, sounds like a really simple starting point. But all they do is m&a. They literally their entire website is just the different types of m&a transactions that they do. And so it's no coincidence that they are the ones that we had found, and everyone had discovered so many butterfly associations with because the butterfly is actually just a common term for something else called a divisive reorganization. And I have to give credit to Sal here, because he's the one that discovered it. And we just been doing a little bit of, you know, searching and research and putting some thoughts together on it since then. But the divisive reorganization is the umbrella term for a bunch of different ways that you can restructure a corporation, whether it's through chapter 11, or not, whether it's a merger, whether it's, you know, two founders, you know, not wanting to work together anymore. Or maybe you know, you otherwise have one, a company that wants to be separated into multiple companies. There are multiple, multiple different kinds of divisive, reorganizations. And, you know, one or two is exactly like what this sounds like is happening with bed bath. So I'll go ahead, buddy.

S Sal 09:12

Yeah. So when we were doing research, and it's insane, because me and Jake, are just two people. Now, I know a lot of people look up to us. And you know, we they think that we know what's going on and stuff. Yeah, we've put a lot of time and effort into trying to understand everything. And there's many aspects of this entire investment that you need to take into consideration. There's the legal side of things. There's the financial, the numbers, there's the employment side, which has directors and you have obviously trademarks, and there's many avenues you have to kind of understand to get into it. And to keep continuously up to date with things is a difficult task. So when we come together and just the two of us and we managed to brainstorm and we find new DD every other day, that potentially leads us to pull on new

threads when we came across this device reorganizations, it was exciting because it looks like the exact tax efficient manner to split off a valuable asset within a company that's locked in. Now, if you think about what Ryan's con obviously suggested to the board, and obviously Jake's gonna break it down into more detail, but I just want to highlight to everyone make a note of those two words divisive, reorganizations have a read into them, if you can find more DD, if you can find precedent, if you can find any other information to help bring it together, there's a hive mind of people, there's 450 of you in here, if me and Jake can find good terms that match just the two of us, then the collective collective consciousness of everyone in here will make a huge difference into uncovering potentially what's going on. I do think we are close to the outcome of this. But at the same time, understanding how it unfolds and understanding what plays out can give you a lot more reassurance, which is why we have unwavering conviction, because there's so many ways this can play out. And a device, every organization is one that is highly possible. However, we can't be guaranteed to be right, we can just find things, connect the dots, and then present them to you guys. Yeah,

J

Jake2b 11:04

well said. And really, this is the whole point of of, you know, writing DD doing spaces going on the TV show, sharing ideas in general, right is, is getting the information out there and then moving the baton a little bit further forward so that everybody else has a better starting point for their own work, right. And so, Sal mentioned a very important element of it, which is the tax advantage, which is really what brings all of these little pieces together. And I don't want to get into that piece now, because that's where I think we'll finish. But I just want to make sure that we discuss the divisive reorganization in order. And so there's a few elements here that I want to go over. One, there's three main types. Either you have a spin off, which everybody knows that's a common one. So a spin off is actually one of one of three main types of divisive, reorganizations, there's two others, one is called a split off. One is called a split up. Now, the with the split up, which is where I believe bed bath is going but before there, I'll just give a little brief summary of each one a spin off, I mean, it's obviously the most most, I guess, commonly known one or the most popular one, it's when you do a distribution of a stock of a, you know, of a corporation that you're invested in. Obviously, it's on a pro rata basis, which means depending on how much you have is how much you'll get. And you give a distribution to the to that Corporation's shareholders. And after the spin off, shareholders own two sets of stock, one of the parent old Corporation, and one of the spin off spun off entity, right, so So that's a spin off is you have to, I guess shares instead of one, then you have a split off, which is where the shareholders are given a vote or a choice. And so what you do is, you know, the Corporation presents a situation where, hey, we're doing a split off here. And you as a shareholder have the choice to surrender some or all or whatever portion of the shares that you like. And you can have those exchanged for the, you know, the split off portion of the business, which is now becoming its own business. Importantly, all of the different types of divisive, reorganizations are where the businesses become separate. And so, you know, this is kind of counterintuitive when you think of the spin off. But I think that is why it has its own specific understanding and its own little type of divisive reorganization is because, yeah, you do have that corporate structure where you have shares of both, but importantly, they are independent businesses. So the split off is where you have, you know, the Corporation says, Hey, you have a vote, or you can choose to surrender however many shares, and you can keep some of the old one, but whatever you do surrender you get in exchange of the new one. Now, a split up is the one that has the best tax advantage and is the one where I believe is the most relatable to Bed Bath and the situation that we're in as common stock shareholders of bed bath, which is called a split up. A split up is where you have a corporation and it has it becomes at least two corporations. So

you know, like this is really the whole point of tonight's space is to tie in a lot of loose ends and tie in a lot of ideas and a lot of different directions that some DD has gone and really put a bit of an umbrella over it, so that you we can paint the picture that it is part of a cohesive idea. And so the split up is you have a new entities formed at least two new entities formed. But then once the new entities are formed, the parent company is liquidated, it is gone. And what happens is the old parent company eliminates its shares, those are gone. And then using what's called Section 17, a three of the you can look that up. That's a law that basically says that brokers and broker dealers and the DTC and the NFCC and all those guys they have to maintain shareholder rights. So even though the shares are gone, your ownership is recorded and everyone knows what you have and what you should get. Because once the old shares are gone, there's again what's called a pro rata distribution of the new company's shares. And so pro rata means, again, based on however many shares you had is, you know, you'll get shares of the new company. But importantly, the old Corporation has to be liquidated and gone first, those shares have to be gone, then after which you can have the distribution of the new shares. Obviously, it's not going to take a genius to realize how that's relatable to the situation we're in. But I think it was worth mentioning just to give one people a little bit of reassurance against some Fudd. Or Or maybe Delta you've been hearing or naysayers saying that you know, the shares are gone, the plan is confirmed, yada, yada, yada. In a split off, that is exactly what has to happen. Right? So you have a corporation, which operates two businesses, and again, I say two or more businesses, because we've noted that, you know, over time since September, we noticed that byebye baby, and the Texas subsidiary BVB YTF appear to have separated from the parent corporation. The old parent company will make these two new corporations, let's call them let's say the parent corporation A and then by babies B and in Texas is C right? Then Corporation a will do a distribution to its subsidiary well, not subsidiaries. Now their corporation B incorporation C after they've liquidated. So they will they will cease to exist. And then a distribution will happen to the those other new corporations, why is this a beneficial way of doing things? Well, it ties in something else together, because a split up is one of the little pieces of it is called a divisive type D reorganization. And that is where you have the most tax advantaged situation. So this is a tax free exchange, there is no tax penalty for the transfer of these shares or for the transfer of ownership into a new company. But it is a little bit of a complicated procedure. And so wait ways it shows us and it demonstrates for us that there is a purpose as to why Deloitte has been doing so much work. And I do want to say actually, now that I mentioned mentioned that, I want to say a quick thank you to Sun Devil for being a great trooper and working on his French because if you've been listening to Sundar lately, he's making fantastic commentary on Lazard and Deloitte, I won't give them away but just make sure you listen to him next time he's on a space because he's he's his French is becoming quite nice. But you know, Deloitte doing a lot of work in the tax area and in the tax arena is really substantiated by this divisive type D reorganization. The really important thing too, and too dirty Vader's credit, when he was looking through the dockets. It was either Gibbons, or the UCC, or Deloitte. I can't remember off the top of my head right now. But there's one mention where they are discussing the section 382 and section 368 of the Internal Revenue Code. And at the time, you know, we had been looking into that and thought, okay, yeah, whatever is Section Three, two, we know because that's the Nol. Plus, there was so much other Nol information in that docket. And there was only one mention of section 368. And I think not knowing what we know, now, not having known it back then. It's obvious that it was missed. But guess what, section 368 is exactly what the divisive reorganization is, it is the portion of the law that deals with the corporate structure of a type D divisive reorganization. So, you know, it kind of really brings a couple like I said, of these ideas back together, where it was all there from the get go, the entire procedure was was outlined, right, the the, the testing for the ownership, making sure that they filed followed IRC 368 and three C 382, which is 368. Now we know is the type D reorganization three two we know is the Nol, making sure that they

preserved enough of the old structure that they have the NOL access that they can utilize the entire benefit, because by the sounds of these dockets, there's been a lot of cancellation of bad debt. And so this is going to be a rather lean company when it emerges. But then now knowing what we know, the butterfly, this, this entire idea of the tax strategy. It all is related, you know, and so the section 368 I'm not going to spend too much time breaking the law because again, I don't want to have a two hour space. But I encourage everybody to look up IRC 368 just like we've looked up IRC 382 in Thai and its entirety it deals with the divisive reorganization, the legal avenue by which you can do this, how you can do the split up. And now importantly, with the type D when you want to have this full access of the following IRC 368 There are some other little ownership bits that answer some other questions because you know, the entire time we've wondered, when you want to access the NOL, you have to preserve 50% of the old company, right through ownership or through business continuity or asset continuity. One thing that I couldn't really reconcile is there was it appeared to me that there were too many hands in the pie. How can you have 50% ownership and not go over 50% When you have Hudson Bay, when you have six treat when you have any sort of affiliates, you know, Hudson Bay, having converted as many warrants as they did, they themselves are approaching 50%. And we've speculated that one of the main reasons, you know, whether it's they don't want to be litigated by the, the DTC sure of why they increase the float. But I think another big reason is that, you know, they also have to account for the fact that we also have Sixth Street doing accredited. And we also have, you know, like I said, Anyone and everyone else, because Sixth Street had cosign that dip had some other, you know, signing friends or affiliates all coming along for the ride. And so all of it really seemed like it was more than 50% ownership. And so I have no idea until I found this where, under a type D, divisive reorganization, you actually need to maintain 80% of the corporate ownership. And this was really another one of those elements that brought it all together and made a lot of unknowns makes sense for me, is because if you now have to meet an 80% threshold, and again, I'm not saying that this is what's happening, this is just obviously the result of the reading we've done. And we may or may not be correct, but it just, it makes sense, putting into perspective alongside everything else. But if now you're working with an 80% number, rather than a 50% number, then things start to fall into place a lot, a lot easier. So again, that's the type D reorganization and that's IRC 368, where they outline that 50% ownership structure. Sal, if you don't mind, if you want to share some thoughts, or I saw you had your hand up earlier, I'm just going to try to find that exact legal definition of the 80%. So I can read it out. And if you wouldn't mind just hopping on for a sec.

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Sal 22:01

Yeah, so I was just, I just reached my follow limit, because I was just following back loads of people that reposted thank you for the sport, everyone. And this is very interesting stuff, because we keep saying it's tax efficient. And if it is, someone like Ryan Cohen or Carl Icahn taking control this company, while they're not going to piss away money on tax for it to go back to the wrong hands eventually, probably end up with short sellers, helping short these stocks again. And we know how Ryan Cohen is very outspoken about government policies, inflation and just the way they use money and all the narratives they paint on mainstream media. He's been vocal about it on his ex account. And also with tax situations, I know you guys are sick of hearing about Texas and California, etc. However, in docket 2899, which is all the court dates coming up, and all the all of the issues that they want to discuss. So there were 13 Texas tax authorities, which were filing documents opposing the debtors, objections to their tax claims and liabilities. Now, the fact that they've got 13 counties, and I think Texas has got 254 counties. And then also within the docket to 899. There was 16 counties in California, that were covering also objections with tax claims and liabilities, and their disputes. And there's only 54

counties in California. So the fact is, these two states are very prominent, they are the only two states which are desperately resolving tax liabilities and claims with the debtors. And this plays into the device of reorganization. Now, as I pointed out a few weeks ago, BBYCF LLC is located within California. Now I know a few people have tried to debunk it by saying oh, what they sold it to cost plus. So there's two things I have an issue with that. First is I don't know how much of the warehouse they actually sold to cost plus. And secondly, I think there was an agreement where they still own it, it was just leased out to them. And this is why it's still under 2026 final decree. It's also why it was one of the subsidiary guarantors for the notes offered in October of 2022. And also, why does this matter? Well, GameStop do 19% of their business in those two states, Texas and California. So it's not unreasonable to assume that he would want valuable store locations within those places. And if we look at everything else comprehensive that's going on to date with dream on me and with everything else we've discussed in the indications towards an equity Carve out or a an emerging entity happening the device every organization is a nice vehicle for that to happen. Because what they want to do is if the acquiring company wants to assume certain liabilities of bed bath, including attack stuff, it makes sense that they would want to resolve them before the acquisition happens. And also this plays in because we have BBY acquisition co LLC registered in mid October in Texas with a tax number. And of course there's the company that is set on buy buy baby right now. And again, we go into buy buy baby, they still haven't renamed a subsidiary. They Everything has been renamed to DK-butterfly, because of the Bed Bath and Beyond trademarks being sold, etc. However buy buy baby hasn't yet it was strictly outlined in the asset purchase agreement. All of this indicates right now, that shared service agreement or a carve out or divisive reorganization is underway. And it's moving forward. And it's helping us to get what we want, which will be shareholder value. Go ahead, Jake.

J

Jake2b 25:22

Yeah, no, that's wonderfully said. I think, you know, this also, you know, obviously, we want to make sure we're not introducing any any bias. But this also really resolves a piece of this dream on me element, right, where they began with such a small IP agreement. And then it was expanded, and then it was expanded. And again, and again and again. Again, IRC 368 really provides a convenient and logical explanation for that activity, right, because I found a little bit about the 80%. But before I get into that, I just want to mention, so you know, in 368, A, which is just titled reorganization, it is either, you know, a standard merger, or whatever. But again, to hear Subsection B and Subsection C, I'll just read C, because I think it's the more relevant one, it is the X acquisition by one corporation of or in exchange solely for all or a part of another corporation, where you acquire all or some or all of a or a part of the voting stock or voting control. And this is where that 80% comes in is because you have a 50% ownership of the company and an 80% ownership of the voting stock is really what it was. So it's subject Subsection C, which defines what's called control. So Subsection C says, to mean that ownership of a stock possessing at least 80% of the total combined voting power of all classes of stock entitled to vote, and at least 80% of the total number of shares of all other classes of stock of the corporation. So that's where it really falls into place where they have the stock, they can take 80%, to make sure that they satisfy IRC 368, which provides them a basically tax free exchange. This is a zero tax acquisition on its face by doing the conversion from the one corporation to the other, the entire benefit of I mean of any butterfly transaction, but specifically the split up and the type D is that you have a very tax advantage situation for the new acquiring entity. How does that tie into a dream on me? Well, if all of these are affiliates, and all of these are part of a, you know, an affiliate group made by Lazard as far back as the dealer manager agreement in October 2022, then we all of a sudden have a very convenient

explanation where this is one corporation, or a legal group of affiliates, taking all of another corporation, liquidating the old Corporation, and then establishing a new one. What does that do? Well, it allows them to have their own like, it's, again, it ties in a lot of a lot of pieces, you don't have to do your own IPO. So you don't have to apply to the SEC, you don't have to do a year or more of accounting practices to justify your balance sheet. They are a valuable company that you use to satisfy the requirements, yada, yada, yada, you don't have to pay expensive lawyers, you don't have to hire companies like KPMG, you don't have to have all of this preparatory work that usually takes I mean, at least a year, we've seen Reddit is preparing for an IPO, they've been going at it for over two years now. I think they're under their third year. So these these things take time. So there is a a value in doing what's called a reverse merger so that you can just take a private company into the shell of an already existing public company, and basically skip all those steps and really expedite that process. But if we want to tie in another element, I think I want to mention one thing that's really stood out as a bit of a hold up for not understanding that how this is happening, but I think we got it maybe backwards. And so again, I'm not saying I'm correct. I'm just putting this out there to the community. And I hope anybody that does feel that they can disprove it, we should. But I think the idea that the ticker was preserved, and tying that to overstock making the IP purchase, I think that that we should have another look at that. I think what really happened, if you look at the language is that overstock took the IP, but the estate kept the ticker. And so this makes a lot more sense to me, in terms of what we're talking about right now, but also in a lot of other facets as well. Because I mean, of course, right now, we're talking about the parent company liquidating or not existing anymore. Right. So, and again, having preserved the ticker for the estate, which is what the exactly the language is, is preserving the ticker for the estates. And what Gibbons and what Andrew Glen were looking at, and what they were trying to establish when they were trying to also reverse the dip is they were looking at is this even possible, there was a lot of time spent analyzing case law, analyzing, analyzing precedent and looking at prior legal decisions to see if this was a maneuver that was allowed. So it tells me that either it's a typical, or they were trying to find basis to make them not be able to do it, where overstock had taken the IP, the name of And they had received whatever they received in their asset purchase agreement. But importantly, the language does say, in the gibbons docket, whether it's allowed, that the estate preserve the ticker, that tells me that overstock did not take the ticker. And that tells me that the estate is saving the ticker for this new corporation. And when there will become a new share issuance down the road, according to a type D reorganization, or a split up, I think that those new shares can easily utilize that old ticker. And again, they can encompass the convenience of a reverse merger and not have to worry about going through any sort of hoops of registering a new identity or a new ticker with the stock exchange or yada yada yada. And I think that also provides a pretty logical explanation of why when overstock had moved from the NASDAQ to the NYSC they did not take on BBB why they changed their ticker to byo n. So I'll go ahead.

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Sal 30:53

Oh, yeah, you literally beat me today. I was just gonna bring up obviously, Overstock had mentioned as soon as they got involved in this deal. Jonathan Johnson was on an interview with CNBC and he said that the ticker is kind of stained with all the bad stuff that happened, obviously, with Gustavo as a short selling and the attack on the price all of that stuff. But one of the dockets did mention that they wanted to preserve the ticker for the estate, there's been a lot of work from Tamar Donegan and obviously other lawyers with securities related matters. They've been analyzing the share count, they've been discussing director restricted stock awards under existing plans. So a lot of work has gone into stock and ticker related activities.

And then the NOLS. You know, we know that the NOLS would affect the ticker as well because of preserving the shareholder structure for the next Corporation. And obviously, who wouldn't want \$1.6 billion in tax write offs over a few years, especially if you know, you could turn this business into 100 stores, which they're planning to, they want to recover money from the maritime lawsuit of 300 mil. So they're alone, you have nearly 2 billion worth of tax credits and potential clawback without any other settlements without any other short squeeze or any of that stuff. So it makes absolute sense. And the ticker is valuable, you know, everyone in here is valuable, the 600 plus of you in here, you can imagine the benefit any company to have a huge, loyal, committed retail holder base. And there's no company that has been through chapter 11, that is classed as a meme stock. And I don't think they could handle it, I think a lot of them would fold, they wouldn't have the due diligence that we do, they wouldn't be able to continue forward the way we have months after the listing. And that is a huge attribute to any company. They would love this sort of following the search engine optimization you guys offer, the fact that everyone would be customers putting the money back into the business, you're a highly valuable asset as shareholders and I think the ticker is a reflection of that also.

J

Jake2b 32:47

Yeah, no, I think this is not a novel concept. As I've said many times before, I think Gamestop in 2021 proved how valuable of an asset retail shareholders are, I think the vigor of retail shareholders since in not giving up and not allowing anyone to kind of brush what happened under the table and the relentless pursuit of uncovering the fraud, uncovering the Ponzi and uncovering, you know, rehypothecation, naked short selling, all of it, I think is really indicative of the fact that retail is a force to be reckoned with. And you see recognition of that, I think happening more and more. I think a lot of institutional investors are looking from the sidelines to see how this is going to play out and they are cognizant of retail shareholders. You know, I think I read yesterday or the day before Paul even had said that, you know, even now we're in February and the guy running phn Ryan Marshall is already considering doing a virtual shareholder meeting because, you know, obviously, they're they're picking up news that there's going to be folks that are going to want to have a bit of a say, or have some sort of involvement in that shareholder meeting. It's so funny to see the you know, everyone recognizes the power of retail, and I think it's one of those things that will never be put back in the box. But I think Sal, you mentioned importantly, I did want to just make sure that I made that distinction about the preserving the ticker for the estates, because like you said, yeah, they beyond has come to the NYSC with their own ticker, allowing the ticker to be preserved and held by the estate. It can only indicate, in my opinion, what we're talking about now, because if it were just a liquidation, then you're going to have a lot of creditors lining up to sue the estate and sue the attorneys because there was not a value maximizing transaction because even if it was \$1, money was left on the table by not giving the ticker away, right. So obviously in the context and in how the language is used of gibbons using case law and spending hours and hours, trying to find precedent and research of why the preservation of the ticker was not allowed, indicates to me that that's something that they were trying to see if they could reverse. So why would the company have not given away the ticker? Well, because in this case, it makes perfect sense. that you would then after liquidating the old parent company, utilize the ticker and having that association with the new shares of the new stock. Funny enough if it weren't, you know more than just convenience we see in all of the bankruptcy filings since I mean at least since May, maybe even since the beginning. And especially in July, bed bath is never referred to as BBB, why Bed Bath and Beyond is referred to BB and B. And BBB. Why is when everyone is talking about byebye baby. So you know, whether that's a coincidence or whether everyone knew from the get go or otherwise, I just think it's

worth noting. And again, the spec or the you know, the LLC that was made on the same day that the amended transaction with dream on me was made. And again, I say dream on me just for simplicity. So we can follow along dream on me are not the entity that made the purchase. But you know, so having dream on me have BBB y acquisition CO and not byebye baby acquisition co well guess what, it took us a while but it turns out they're one in the same thing. Because no one is referring to Bed Bath and Beyond not even dream on me themselves in the lawsuit with go global, even go global having pursued a going concern for byebye baby is referring to it as BBB why. So you know, it makes sense if this was the intention, or you know if this is what they wanted to do, but at the very least, it substantiates this line of thinking that this could be a split up or a type D reorganization, I just want to highlight on top of what I said about having the 80% of the voting power, or 80% of the ownership of all of the outstanding classes of stock. This also makes sense that all of Hudson Bay would have been converted into common stock. And all of the RSUs or the RSA that are granted to directors had been addressed by Tamar and the other associates and attorneys with Kirkland in July is because they want to make sure that when they entered September, they had one class, there was one class of stock and its common stock. Hudson Bay was the only derivative owning owning entity with warrants and was preferred shares, they were immediately converted in May, we noticed that going into July. I mean, we didn't really realize it until September with the SEC filings. But it had been shared with us that in July, there was 180 outstanding shares of preferred stock that were not converted. Then suddenly, as soon as the dream on me asset purchase agreement is finalized. And as soon as the form 25 is revealed by the NASDAQ and shared publicly, well, all of a sudden a bunch of things are changing. And suddenly those remaining 180 are converted, suddenly, there's no more, you know, outstanding derivatives, suddenly, the TSO has gone up from 739 to 782 million coincidence, intentional, I don't know, I don't think we're gonna have to wait very long to find out. Going alongside with the idea about having 80% of the voting power and the control and all of the asset classes. Another thing that IRC 368 discusses that is really applicable, I think, to the situation we're in. And I did read a little bit of the Internal Revenue Code. It's called Title 26. It's on page 1017, that's 1017. If you read the Internal Revenue Code under Section 368, under the section of F, and then F, subsection three, you know, F really deals with F and E deal with a mergers using voting stock of a corporation with a controlling merged Corporation, which I think in its own is a little bit applicable, but I don't want to get into the weeds on different structuring. But subcomponent F of title 368 says, certain transactions involving two or more investment companies. And so I thought it was quite funny, you know, and yeah, it took me a long time to read the Internal Revenue Code. But you know, it was wild to see confirmation that there is a specific subsection there. If you have either, again, a dealer manager agreement, or Sixth Street and a group of affiliates, or maybe someone acting as a proxy, you know, trying to have involvement in this type of the reorganization or a split up, they are accounted for in a specific manner of addressing this and having the tax preservation. Specifically, they have to meet a requirement that they are an investment company. And what did we just discuss on the sixth street space the other day was the earnings call that cell had. Sixth Street themselves is classified as a business development company, which is one of three types of investment companies governed by the Securities Act of 1940. So again, we have a confirmation that they're accounted for legally, there's an avenue with which they themselves can be doing this, which substantiates the credit bid substantiates the ownership substantiates the fact that Hudson Bay, which is also an investment company, was also somehow involved in this because they have an enormous common stock position that was not sold off. We know that because we have confirmation of their warrants being converted in May, after judge Papandrea had said that they are not allowed to be making any sort of sales without prior application to the court and a judge hearing on it and the judge after offering a ruling that they can none of which occurred, which we know it didn't occur. So they have their common stock position. They're an investment Companies Sixth Street is an investment company. Anyone co

signing on the dip is also an investment company. If you look through them, they're registered with the SEC as being such, some of them are actually Sixth Street subsidiaries, but even they are addressed in the specialty lendings subdivision of Sixth Street in their filings as being investment companies themselves. But for some point three of subsection F, it says that investment company means a regulated Investment Company, which obviously we have confirmation of Sixth Street. And this corporation has a 50% or more of the value of whose total assets of stock and securities and 80% of the value of those assets are held for investment. And so we know that this is happening, of course, because alongside the credit bid, alongside Hudson Bay, holding the common stock that they do this really, like I said at the beginning answers this situation of how is the how high is the enterprise value really going to be to make sure that they satisfy that 50% threshold? And again, I don't want to say that I'm correct, because I don't know if I am. But this is a really easy answer of well guess what they don't have to, they actually have to qualify for a higher threshold, which is 80%. And when they do qualify for the 80%, when they do issue that new stock from these new corporations, it is not a tax incurring event. So that I'm just going to end that little segment there. And I'm going to pull up my next slide, Sal or chat, if you want to add anything, go ahead and I'll be back in about 30 seconds. Once I get my window up here. I

S

Sal 41:26

feel like a cheap philosopher, just in between kind of porn rounds while Jake's just doing rounds and going toilet enough to come in and keep everyone hot and wet. Anyway polti Put up a tweet today. And it was a picture of Ryan Cohen. And it was a screenshot. And I think the screenshot may be from Alpha states video. It's the exact same shot that's in it. So this is quite interesting. And it's in black and white. And obviously, we think that Gamestop is under a blackout period right now. So I thought that was quite interesting. It matches up with what's going on polti Put the emoji with the finger of its mouth saying to shush. So perhaps he thinks that there's a blackout period in place to we know, unfortunately, it's difficult for him to even express his opinion on some of the stuff that's going on, because of the way that the media will come for him. They'll target his family, they'll target him personally. And you know, we always say for someone have a high net worth to put themselves out there like that. And they know they're gonna get attacked by short sellers and all this short and distorted tactics. I mean, Ryan can barely says a word. He hardly tweets he does zero news interviews don't even speak on His own earnings calls. Yet they just continuously find time to ship talk him. He also has never taken \$1 In compensation never sold a single share during the Gamestop run up at 21. Yet they accused him of doing a pump and dump when Jake Freeman literally did a fucking pump and dump marketers and pumped and dumped the company for years. And they said nothing bad about them. So the fact is polti knows who his enemies are. He has to put out stuff perhaps in indirect obviously, that's just my opinion. I don't know if it is or not. But it to me, you know, I believe they are in a blackout period. And we've spoken about this many times. Why would they not buy shares at these low prices? Ryan Cohen put in 10 million at twice the price that it is right now. It makes no sense. I've stopped believing in the company or something more is going on. And I find it very unbelievable. That these ridiculously low prices that Larry Chang wouldn't at least buy like 1000 shares, or Daniel more or Alan Attell or Ryan corn wouldn't put another million in. So that's what it seems like to me. Jake, are you back?

J

Jake2b 43:36

Yeah, no, I've been back for a while. I'm just glad you mentioned Daniel more because again, in

the context of how complicated this legal and tax accounting is, it really makes sense. The Daniel Moore is at the helm for GameStop. Why is he

S Sal 43:53

100%. This has always been a key thing for me is that he could have hired a CFO with a broad range of experience suitable to the role. Instead, he hires and he specifically says interim CFO, while the interim for what what the fuck is the company going to do? And then you look at the investment policy, you look at the trademarks and everything that's happened today. The only points to one way that he's taking baby.

J Jake2b 44:16

Absolutely. I think the fact that Daniel Moore is in the PFL position and as a CEO as CFO has not been assigned. And Daniel Moore's specialties are all tax going back, what 20 years. I think he's there for a purpose. I do believe I mean, at this point, this either has to be related to GameStop, you know, through their new investment policy that they want to become a mutual fund or a business that you know, extracts the value and gains for their own stock and shareholders by having other businesses that generate revenue. Maybe this is the perfect answer to Gamestop kids. Maybe this is the perfect launching pad for the E commerce giant that he's wanted and tried to do for a long time. Daniel Moore must be somehow involved in this and his expertise aligns with everything that we're talking came out tonight Chad go for a buddy.

C chadmojo 45:02

And also don't forget, when that Furlong was his contract was up, you know, checking his LinkedIn, he's still not doing anything. I think he's like a consultant or something for for whatever, but he's he's still kind of out there available. Maybe waiting for an opportunity, because I don't believe that Ryan Cohen would would troll on the day that he got let go saying Not for long. I think that's a kind of a, I guess a double double entendre or whatever. So there's also that too, so there might be something in the wings for him to slide into.

J Jake2b 45:45

Well said, my man, and also I think that was a huge nod to the retail community by taking the not for long joke. I think that was a recognition of like, hey, like, I see you guys. We're all on the same team. But yes, I'll go for it.

S Sal 45:58

Yeah, I was gonna put up a post this week, just reminding people. I had a good post on my own account. Obviously, it got taken down. But the whole thing with Matt funnel never made sense. It was exactly after his two years it ended. Some people had said that there was a no compete with Amazon, which I haven't really seen anywhere. But if you look at Matt furlongs, LinkedIn,

he was with Procter and Gamble for 12 years. He was at Amazon, Australia for eight years. And his role in Amazon was category scaling. So certain categories, he would be in charge of scaling those up. Then he moves to GameStop for two years. And he leaves and it's very distasteful for Ron Cohen to make a comment that's derogatory towards him, simply because Matt Furlong has helped him make the company towards free cash flow, reduce the debt, reduce the stores, keep it profitable. And I think he's been his right hand, man. Now, you could argue, okay, perhaps he had performance issues, which is why he had to let him go. I don't agree simply because if he had performance issues, I don't think it would take Ryan Cohen two years to weed that out and get rid of him. I think he would have been kicked to the curb a year before with micro Supra, who was let go the year after his contract and he was at the same time as Matt Furlong. And also with regards to far along And I'll put this out in a tweet this week as well. Yes, as Chad mentioned, he is a board member and it just says advisor self employed since June 23. Now if you're a CEO level your your CV says three companies, big companies, Procter Gamble, Amazon and GameStop. Why would you have a random untitled CEO? Why would you not want people to know where you're working as a part of your resume as part of your credibility as part of your employees network. And LinkedIn is such a social media kind of element right now people are using it for dating and stuff. That's how popular LinkedIn is. So the fact is still blank is very interesting to me. And very telling before I carry on Jake, did you end up you

J

Jake2b 47:41

know, I just I didn't want to interrupt you. But just to add to both of your points about Matt Furlong. It would be very like, like you said, distasteful for him to be rubbing it in his face like that. And so I don't think that's what it was at all. I think to uh, you have to understand that Matt for a long as a young guy, he's 42 he's come from Amazon. He's come from like you said, Procter and Gamble now haven't been a Gamestop he would not be inactive since leaving Gamestop and just doing nothing I mean, this this untitled CEO role there's way more to it like you said, I firmly believe as well. I think the not for long is a hot tip to one the community but also indicative of the plans for Matt Furlong because, you know, Sal, you've educated me and and others numerous times as well to say that Matt Furlong was really someone that Ryan Cohen, you know, personally picked for the role. I don't think he spent as much time as he did, discovering, you know, chasing him and finding him and really doing his homework on if this was a good fit to then suddenly say no, you know what, now that you've got the job, you're a giant piece of garbage and interaction. Oh, great. There's no way you've told me that him and Matt for a long go back to the chewy days.

S

Sal 48:44

This was the next point when he actually joined GameStop. He there was. So Ryan Cohn obviously went through a very stringent process of hiring people. We know he takes people valuable. And seriously, he wouldn't just put anyone as a CEO to run the company that he's a chairman of that he's got a huge amount of his net worth invested into. Now he went through this process for a while he interviewed many people himself personally. And he picked Matt furlong, and him and Matt Furlong had actually been discussing potential positions since chewy. So they've been in contact since at least 2016, perhaps. So the fact is, you know, you've got a guy that's gone through a rigorous process of interviewing and stuff like that, a multi stage process I've interviewed for high level positions, and you can have so many stages to the

interview process. It's very rigorous. And that's not even with a CEO of like Ryan Cohen, that's just with an average kind of CEO or director or whatever. So the fact is that he went through the process, he took his time he picked him personally. He worked with him for two years. So it's clear to me that he's out for a bigger role. This was his whole purpose. He was part of the transformation within GameStop. They moved it towards where they needed to Ryan Cohen said himself during his interview with Jimmy Diddy, he said that he doesn't want to be CEO again because it nearly killed him at Chewy. Well, a few months later, he takes up the CEO isn't a Gamestop, which is again, a temporary position. I can't see him staying in this for more than another six to nine months maximum. He's put himself as CEO. And when he wrote the letter to Bed Bath and Bye Bye, he did say I'm not in a position to currently oversee the change with Bed Bath and Bye Bye baby that he was suggesting because of his role with GameStop. Well, I think he's achieved what he wanted to have a lot of Gamestop Yeah, there is a lot of still systematic changes that are gonna happen perhaps with the web three side of things, or the metaverse, so we don't know what he's been working on in the background with Matt Firestone or Daniel Wang or whatever. However, looking at everything he's done and everything he said, this is part of a transit transition period. Right now. He's outlined investment policy saying that he's going to invest in other companies securities using game stops cash on hand, essentially making games so as he ventures he does, he hires Daniel Moore as an interim CFO, he gets rid of Matt Furlong. All of these actions are all actions related to a transition period. And it looks like he's about to acquire something, and there's no other company has expressed as much interest in as Bye Bye baby.

J

Jake2b 51:03

Oh, absolutely. And I mean, he wrote a letter to the board, and he tried acquiring stock, and he tried doing it himself. You know, like you said, there's so many things at play here. And I think so many things are going to come together so well and eloquently at the end. But you know, not the least of which like you said, he spent so much time headhunting Matt, for long, it doesn't make sense to just, you know, consider all that time wasted. And for now, Matt, for a long to also not be marketing himself for the next opportunity. I mean, it's just not consistent with a guy who was in the peak of his career going from, you know, like a launchpad into his into his, you know, more senior years as an as a corporate executive, why would he be sitting around on the sidelines? It just, it doesn't make sense. Absolutely. Going back, unless you guys wanted to add anything else about about that little element we had there. With the divisive reorganization, I just want to mention a few other things. When you have, like we mentioned the 80%, or control of 80% of the old company's voting stock, right? They also saw that it satisfies Internal Revenue Code section 368. Now, the first little tidbit of it, you know, a one says that the distributing corporation must transfer assets to one or more new corporations, and that the distributing corporations and or its shareholders must be in control of the corporation immediately after the transfer. And that the distributing corporation must distribute these shares stock or securities of the new corporation pursuant to a plan of reorganization that satisfies the requirements of code, Internal Revenue Code 355. So that introduces a new little bit. The fact that that is mentioned in Internal Revenue Code 368. And the fact that there's only one mention of 368 in the dockets. But importantly, it is there alongside also 382. I think that tells a lot, I think that really substantiates the idea of the split up, I think it really explains why Hudson Bay has the common stock position. I think it explains why everything is going to happen all at once at the end. One, you have to make sure that you satisfy the change of control requirement and don't have more than one. So you save the Nol to According to section 368. Here, you can't do this until the old parent corporation is liquidated and gone. Three, you have to do the stock distribution immediately after the transfer, which is immediately after the

credit bid, which is immediately after the change in control. Lastly, to satisfy one of the sections of this new one, I mentioned 355, you have to be doing business immediately after the transfer, you can't do this. And this is the one important thing is to protect the integrity of the whole idea. You can't do this divisive reorganization structuring just for a tax advantage. You have to have a new business that exists. You have to have this business and actively registered business conducting business and having what's called a continuity of business. And I'll get into that in a second. But importantly, that I think is also a big element of why things are happening in the order that they are and why they're all going to happen at once. I won't repeat myself just for the elements I just said, again, the control elements, the investment companies have to control at least 80% of the voting power of all stock classes, and at least 80% of all of the shares of all of the classes. Again, a very logical and convenient explanation for how Hudson Bay can own as some math has shown half the float and why there's also room for Sixth Street as well if they do a debt to equity conversion, and if they become shareholders themselves, that would satisfy the at least 80%. Now the one other thing I want to mention about section 355 is the distribution. So the distribution under 355 requires like we just said that the shareholders and security holders receive in exchange old securities for new securities, the district You should have this new controlled corporation or sorry, the old Corporation stock will be a tax free if the distributing corporation does all at which is 80%, or more as defined in the law, if they do all of the the distribution of the stock that it owns in the controlled corporation. So what does that mean? That then the old parent entity does the distribution to the new shareholders, and they have to receive, as we said, 80% or more, and then they have to satisfy another one, which is being an active trader business. And so that just outlines as well that you can't do this just for a tax preservation strategy. Sal, go ahead. Before I get into that one, I

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Sal 55:40

just wanted to ask, do you think that the Hudson be the amount of shares they own play into this? If it is perhaps ranking behind that, too?

J

Jake2b 55:48

Absolutely. Yes, absolutely. I think if anything, this, this structuring and this play by Hudson Bay that they affected in February, made sure that this was the only way it could play out. I think that this could also be why the dip was so aggressively pursued to be have been removed, because I think Sixth Street and Hudson Bay or whoever is utilizing them as a proxy, or whatever affiliate is funding or requesting their services knew that this was like the equivalent of a one two punch, by having the ownership through Hudson Bay, you make sure that going into chapter 11, you will have the level of distribution that you need. By having Sixth Street alongside you, establishing super priority, you can make sure that when the cookie crumbles, everything is left and all of the assets can be distributed according to how you want them to. Because again, Hudson Bay, having been converted to common shares is a class nine, right Hudson Bay is at the end of the end of the line just like everybody else. But having Sixth Street at the front of the line. If they're having an affiliate agreement through the dealer manager agreement, they can make sure that they have interests that are aligned, and they can protect their own interests, and they can make sure that whatever is distributed by Sixth Street complies with what Hudson Bay wants? Absolutely. I think the fact that Hudson Bay, I think Hudson Bay would not be able to have and we would not be able to have this divisive reorganization, if Hudson Bay did not have the level of share position that they did. And again,

this is a really clean way that answers a really big unknown for me going into now was how are they making sure that this ownership will not be above 50% To satisfy the NFL, because again, you can do that, but you just have to establish an enormous enterprise value. And so you know, yeah, Holly Outland said this was a \$5 billion company. But if Hudson Bay has over 300 million shares, and you're going to do a fair market valuation of this company, you have to have a, you know, an asset multiple that I think was a little bit unexpected, and I didn't know really how to navigate that. But again, this solves that problem, because now the threshold is actually 80%. And it's not ownership of the actual company, it's 80% of the voting power of all classes of the stock, and 80% of all stock types. So you can have this satisfaction of having all or a majority of the shares. Plus you can have the 50% new ownership of the new company structure to satisfy the Nol as well. Right. And this is another reason that I think the interplay between Hudson Bay and Sixth Street makes sense is because one has secured the one end, which is the 368. And the three, two, and the other has secured one, the company, obviously, and the control to make sure that the outcome happens according to plan through chapter 11. So a great point. So thank you for bringing that up. Again, like I said, the Active Trader business, I think is really important too, because this is just to make sure just like the NFL, you can't use this to like, just have a tax offset strategy. Just like you can't take over a company to preserve the Nol just to help yourself with a bad tax situation and having like a write off, you can't utilize a divisive reorganization or a butterfly to be able to give yourself a tax advantaged position as well, because, again, this stock transfer from the old corporation to the one or more new corporations is a tax free event if you are doing, you know, business immediately after. So, one last thing about 355. You know, a corporate division must be carried out for one or more corporate business purposes, right. And it says here, this is because a tax free treatment is applied to distributions that are a part of restructurings of corporate operations that are required for these business purposes. And so again, you know, the last thing that I mentioned here, and the one thing I wanted to share was just the mechanism by which they do it, which is that they do a pro rata distribution by doing a distribution to shareholders either through a dividend or through a, you know, just a exchange of you had old shares of old company, we have your records now that the old company is liquidated, you know, you can have a new distribution of the new shares of this corporation. And then you have two little things that have come up before with the Nol as well. Just as a tax. You know, not you know, I guess an anti loophole, two of which one of which is continuity of business enterprise which satisfies a lot of the same Nol one. And I don't need to go into that too much, but the other one is called continuity of interest. And so continuity of interest is funny, because, you know, this is again, not for the NFL, this is strictly for the divisive reorganization and preserving a tax free status for transferring these shares to one corporation to another. It's called continuity of interest, you satisfy continuity of interest, if one or more owners of the new company was an owner of the old company, that I think so I didn't want to mention it answering your question, but that is where Hudson Bay really plays into it is because by having the common stock position that they did the drift, the fact that it was a derivative position leading up until the bankruptcy I think was a very strategic move. One, they do specify that on February 8 in their SEC filing when they come with the equity offering that following you know, the Securities Act of 1933, section three a nine, we're not going to make any more SEC filings or disclosures, when we do any conversions, any of these warrants that we acquire, we're not making, you know, further disclosure, because we're doing what's called the cashless exercise. When you do a cashless exercise, it basically means, you know, no matter what it is, there's no money involved. It's like, I give you money, you give me shares, because that's the agreement, you do not require follow up filing up until the end of chapter 11. At that point, who cares, because the whole thing set up, right, like the Kirkland attorneys spent 19 hours, some of them worked on a Sunday, to make sure that the dip was ready by 2pm. On Monday, for Judge Metalia to sign the NFL order. And to make sure that nobody could go over 4.5 Or anybody over cannot dispose to make sure

that they went under, the change of control was preserved, the strategic nature was preserved, everything was ready to go. And this is why I think Sixth Street came with the 100 million dollar cash infusion in February, because they were at risk of this plan not working out. Again, it was one of those things that I thought and I suggested by had no real reason to believe it, or substantiate it rather. But really, the reason is, is that they needed to buy time so that Hudson Bay could acquire the shares, and give bed bath the money. That is why Hudson Bay went ahead throughout March making three amendments to lower the strike price so that the company could keep doing this exchange. And then we saw the stock price being tortured, down, down, down and never hitting the strike price. So at the end of the day, on March 30, Hudson Bay says, You know what, whatever, we're just gonna have a period of time where there's no strike price. Ask yourself, What does that mean for any sort of value preservation for Hudson Bay, if they're saying, I just give us the shares, it doesn't matter what the stock price was, the stock price at that point was 57 cents. And they still said, Yeah, okay, sure, whatever, there's no threshold, just take whatever you want. Now, Hudson Bay had signed up for up to a billion dollars, they only extracted another 100 50 million on top of the 225 in that little window, when the company could have taken the you know, the entire rest to make it a billion. Why did they not take more because they only forced Hudson Bay to convert an amount of shares that was proportionate to the ownership that they wanted of the new company. There was a threshold, it was it was hit, they made sure that they were okay. They left some of the shares as preferred as derivatives, because first they had to adjust the TSO, they didn't want to make they wanted to make sure that Hudson Bay didn't go over. As soon as they did adjust the TSO, the exercise the remainder, and we have the last satisfaction of section 355, which is the continuity of interest, which is a owner that held an ownership stake in the old company holds a stake in the new company. That's all I wanted to say. The other thing is just reminding everyone, the reason Lazard called this a butterfly, the reason Lazard in April or May in their email said, Hey, our email address for this project is project butterfly. It's because it's a divisive reorganization, we think I think there's a lot to substantiate it. I think there's a lot that we just discussed over the past hour that would that would validate that line of thinking, salary or chat unless you guys have anything else to add. That's all I wanted to mention. I just really felt that this was a compelling argument of why things have happened, how they did, it explains a lot of loosens. It also gives us a lot of insight into why Deloitte was doing a lot of the work they were doing, again, mentioning section 368, which before we discovered the divisive reorganization really didn't make sense of how it fit into everything else. But again, now having known that having seen why Lazard utilize the name butterfly, which is just an everyday term for this, I encourage everybody to look up split ups, split offs and spin offs. They're the three main types of divisive organizations. Yeah, that's all I had to say. What do you guys think?

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Sal 1:04:38

Yeah, great. Very good space. As always, everyone, you know, if you've listened, I'll put it on Spotify shortly too, just in case you didn't get to hear all of it. Otherwise, just repurpose the space. You know, it does work an extra lot of people but Spotify is just an easier platform for people to listen to it on. And it is not monetized. And even if it was Who gives a fuck I would make \$1 a year I just wanted to cover quickly. So AJ is very keen on his date for the 24th, which is Saturday, actually next Saturday, he thinks that we're gonna get an announcement and probably before on that day, he's put up a few tweets about it. So I'll just read out one of his that he put up recently. He said 24th of February Take it or leave it. I really don't think our C section 1616. Below Sue is a reason to delay m&a News. Put yourself in his shoes, or that rhymes. Worst case scenario, he boats and returns the measly 60 mil profit and settles the case. I personally don't think the crystal ball was alluding to ABC or the 16 B lawsuit. Everyone

is entitled to their opinion, of course, I genuinely believe as self centered as it sounds that his tweet was prompted by the hundreds of us who engaged with his tweet when it was posted. If you don't think RC is a man who had this plan laid out years in advance, you don't know RC, if he wasn't signaling the announcement date with this frog and ice cream emoji tweet. What alternative explanation is there? What are we waiting for regarding acquisition is it's time I'm reiterating this here since it did not get much coverage on the PBS show last night 24th of February 2024. So he's very keen on this date. I just wanted to kind of get your thoughts on it. What do you think? Do you think there could be a plausible day? Yeah,

J

Jake2b 1:06:18

absolutely. I think, you know, knowing knowing that we've seen the tax authorities settled before the hearing beforehand, I mean, indicates that of course it can happen again. And it's obviously not a novel concept. I have some thoughts about the 16 V. But I don't want to get into that. Because I mean, at the end of the day right now, it's it's whatever. But I think the most important thing from that AJ tweet, is the idea that, you know, he does mention the frog, right. And if the frog is indicative of the Leap Year, I think it's really cool to long the preparation for this move was taking.

S

Sal 1:06:57

Oh, yeah, you guys, you blocked it out for a second, repeat or not?

J

Jake2b 1:07:01

It said, reconnecting. Okay. So I just wanted to say if he if he is correct about the frog, representing a leap year, I think it's really cool to realize and think about the how much planning and how long and how far in advance this play had had begun. Right, like Ryan Cohen in 2021, when he made was that 21 or 22? He made that tweet. I don't remember. You know? Yeah. Okay. So if it if it is relating to this, I think it's wild. You know, how far ahead of time these guys do this planning? Obviously, we've seen this Carl Icahn do a lot of this, you know, where it does take a long time, he's indicated that in the shareholder letter, and I think we waited long enough, like you said, I think there's nothing to say that this has to take much longer. Everything else is out of the way. A lot of the other issues are settled, you know, and so we're now tying up loose ends. I think there's nothing wrong with February 24. About the section 16 B. Yeah, you know what, I love that he's challenging the thinking, I think everybody should I wish more people would my only thing and you know, I won't get into too much in depth. But you know, I would think, just from a logical perspective, if if you think that the section 16 B is irrelevant, or that the company is going to get the profit of the discouragement of the profits. Why would Todd and Judy be pursuing it, because really, they would have no gain, they would have a lot of legal expense. And they would just have a lot of headache, but but nothing to show for it at the end of the day if the company was getting it. So that's something I want to talk about more with AJ. Now we should get them on a space, chat about it, have a good little back and forth or get them on the peepee show. I think it'd be fantastic. And it'd be really nice. I think it'd be good to talk about it some more, because it's great to have differing opinions. Yeah, I've

S

Sal 1:08:33

asked him to to get on the space with us. He's always been a kind of well respected figure within the community. And you can tell why he's he's very intelligent. He's very well spoken, he thinks deep about stuff. So um, he doesn't really set dates. And he's been kind of critical about people setting dates previously. So for him to set a date like this. He's obviously got enough belief in the substance behind it, personally. And as I said, I've got a lot of respect for AG. I just don't think that they would announce it within this coming week. Obviously, if they do amazing, we can shut the shields up and have our space laughing for one hour sooner. Personally, I think March the 11th. I've got a few reasons for that. One is I think the Gamestop earnings is due around March the sixth. So if I expect them to delay the earnings a little bit, major Monday, Monday, the 11th is also the one underneath the deadline for since the plan was confirmed is March the 12th. So I think we've everything I've seen so far, I think they're doing everything as close to deadlines as possible. And I do think Ryan Cohen could have planned this out years in advance. If you just use the earning dates and certain timelines as kind of cut off dates and deadlines throughout the process, then perhaps it's possible. I mean, we saw that as soon as they entered chapter 11. They wanted to deregister delisted securities from day one. They had filed and prepared the form 15 or 25. offline, which one it was, but that was prepared like mid April last week early May so they were planning to delist the securities for quite a while. A holiday Island did one is September the 29th day They really pushed for that. So it looks like they have worked towards a deadline. And even so much so that the creditors were complaining they couldn't monetize the NOLS because the speed of the chapter 11. And if they're doing it with speed, it shows they're in control. If they're in control, it shows as a strategy. And as I love to say, it's been strategic with purpose and intent since day one.

J

Jake2b 1:10:21

Yeah, no, absolutely. And actually, I think that's really good. I think a lot of the a lot of the loose ends get get answered with the divisive organization as well. You know, since we mentioned, the TV show, I just want to make make sure we make a mention to say that I hope he's okay. He had shared that his grandpa passed away, obviously, it's a difficult time for him. So everybody, show him some love and send them a message and tell him you're thinking about him and his family. You know, it's a really, really hard thing to go through. So I hope everybody

S

Sal 1:10:49

peepees got a lot of haters. A lot of these SIG fox will probably use it as fuel and just laugh at it or whatever. If you're a supporter of PPE, if you love what he's done, and the information he's helped provide over the last year or two, despite being dogs, despite being personally attacked, regularly, hated by so many people, just a message, showing them a bit of love, whether it's on his posts, whether it's in a DM, it can go a long way. And I know there's many of you people that do love and appreciate the stuff he does. So just saying that'd be a recognition can really help especially when someone's going through shit.

J

Jake2b 1:11:23

Yeah, absolutely. Absolutely. It's it's a hard time for him. So I hope everybody shows him support. Oh, and one more thing I remembered that I want to make sure that I shared just

support. Oh, and one more thing I remembered that I want to make sure that I shared just about this happening is that everybody should understand the intention here is to know that